

INTEGRATION OF SERVICES FOR NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASE WEEK TO SCREEN AT RISK POPULATION IN COLOMBO RDHS AREA, SRI LANKA

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BACKGROUND

- **Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs)** have emerged as the leading cause of mortality worldwide, accounting for approximately **74% of all deaths globally** and affecting low- and middle-income countries due to urbanization, aging, poor diets, inactivity, tobacco, and alcohol use.
- NCDs now account for **approximately 83% of all annual deaths in Sri Lanka**, making them the **dominant cause of mortality** and a major contributor to national healthcare costs.
- There are **36 healthy lifestyle centers** that carry out NCD Screenings in Colombo RDHS area for total eligible population of **709,437**.
- District's previous year 2024 **covered 4.59%** of empaneled population with **quarterly average number** of NCD Screenings of **9,709**.

DESCRIPTION OF THE INITIATIVE

- A **week-long NCD screening** and awareness program was implemented aimed to **screen 5,000** at-risk individuals according to national protocols providing comprehensive screenings, providing health education, and encouraging timely medical follow-up and lifestyle modification.
- **Outreach Screening programs** were Planned to improve service coverage through Public Health Nursing Officers (PHNOs) coordination .
- **The integration of services** across hospitals, Primary Medical Care Units (PMcus), Medical Officer of Health (MOH) offices, and community-based health platforms contributions **without disrupting their routine services.**

METHODS USED FOR EVALUATION

The **number** of Healthy Lifestyle Clinics (HLCs) functioned and the **coverage**.

RESULTS

- **All 36** Healthy Lifestyle Centres (HLCs) operated through existing service delivery channels **parallel to outreach events**.
- **21 Outreach programs** were coordinated with district-wide support from Public Health Nursing Officers (PHNOs). Multiple health care institutions **collaborated** in some events to overcome **limited staff and resources**.
- In contrast to the district's previous quarterly average of 9,709 screenings, **over 3,500 individuals** were screened **within just one week** during **outreach events** of NCD Week, **achieving over 70 percent of the intended coverage**.

List of **few** Outreach events conducted

- Padukka Weekly Fair
- Makumbura Multimodal Transport Center
- Kottawa Bus Stand
- Meegoda Weekly Fair
- KIU University
- Nawagamuwa Devalaya (Temple)
- Kaduwela Divisional Secretariat
- State Engineering Corporation of Sri Lanka
- National Medicines Regulatory Authority
- Battaramulla Divisional Secretariat
- Oruwala Temple
- Kahatuduwa Market
- Hanwella Bus Stop
- Nawagamuwa Star Packaging

RESULTS CTD.

- **Daily meetings** with PHNOs enabled real-time identification of operational challenges and on-the-ground solutions, while **selected daily data reports**, instead of the usual comprehensive monthly reporting, facilitated timely monitoring, identification of gaps, and continuous improvements.
- Government affiliated institutions and Community-based organizations helped in **dissemination of the messages** to the public on the NCD week and **preparation of the venues for screening**.
- **Private sector partners** assisted with logistics . A **mobile medical unit**, provided by a private sector, facilitated outreach coverage.

LESSONS LEARNT

- The **integration of services into existing health infrastructure** enabled efficient and broad coverage of NCD screening activities without interrupting routine care.
- **Early planning, integrated resource use, and responsive management** were key to the program's effectiveness and adaptability.
- **political sensitivities** and **permissions from venues** affecting program execution reinforced the need for early risk assessment and **official clearances**.

SIMPLE PERSONAL MEDICAL RECORD (PMR) SHEET IS USED TO COLLECT DATA

Screening Program for Non-Communicable Diseases - Colombo

Personal Medical Record

01. Personal Details

Serial No:	Date:
Name:	
NIC No:	Male / Female:
Age:	Date of Birth:
Address:	
Contact No (Mobile):	

02. Anthropometric measurements

Weight (kg):		Height (cm):	
BMI (kg/m ²):		Waist Circumference (cm):	

03. Biochemical Investigations

Random Glucose Level (mg/dl)	
Fasting Glucose Level (mg/dl)	
Serum Cholesterol Level (mg/dl)	

04. Visual Acuity

Right Eye	Left Eye
6/	6/

Notes/Referrals:

5. Past medical/surgical/allergic history

6. Family history

Diabetes	Cancer
Hypertension	Ischemic Heart diseases
Stroke	Asthma and COPD
Kidney disease	Other

07. Behavior risk factors

Physical Activity Levels	Sedentary:	
	Moderate Intensity:	
	Vigorous Intensity:	
Tobacco Smoking	Current Smoker:	
	Quit (Less than 1 year before):	
Betel chewing with tobacco or areca nut	Current User:	
	Quit (Less than 1 year before):	
Other tobacco or areca nut products use	Current User:	
	Quit (Less than 1 year before):	
Alcohol Consumption	Current User:	
	Quit (Less than 1 year before):	

08. Risk assessment

Blood pressure (mmHg)		
Risk Percentage for Cardiovascular Diseases (Non-Laboratory based Risk Factors chart)	<10%	
	10% - <20%	
	20% - <30%	
	≥30%	

09. Breast Examination for Breast Cancer /Abnormalities

Notes/Referrals:

10. Pap smear for Referral for Cervical Cancer

Family History of Cervical Cancer	Yes (Y) or No (N) :
Pap Smear done before or not:	Yes (Y) or No (N) :
Sample collected	Yes (Y) or No (N) :
Notes/Referrals:	

CONCLUSIONS

- **The NCD Week successfully promoted early NCD risk detection and community awareness. Over 3500 Patients screened** through outreach events alone with actual numbers including HLCs likely higher.
- **This initiative highlighted the importance of early planning, strong intersectoral collaboration, data governance guidelines and adaptability in implementing large-scale health programs.**
- **Future programs should prioritize stakeholder coordination and flexible contingency planning.**

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